

Uranium (VI) Complexes of *o*-Hydroxybenzaldoxime and Sodium-1-Naphthol-2-Sulphonate

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Uranium (VI) complexes of *o*-hydroxybenzaldoxime (HBA) and sodium-1-naphthol-2-sulphonate (SNDS) have been studied potentiometrically using Calvin-Bjerrum *pH*-titration technique. HBA is diprotic, the values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ being respectively 12.05 and 8.95. SNDS is monoprotic, and $\log K_1^H$ is 9.89. Uranium forms 1:1 and 1:2 complexes both with HBA and SNDS. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are respectively 13.91 and 8.96 for the HBA complexes; and 7.92 and 6.42 for the SNDS complexes.

In continuation with our previous work¹⁻⁶ on the stepwise equilibria in complex forming systems, uranium complexes of *o*-hydroxybenzaldoxime (trivial name salicylaldoxime, abbr. HBA) and of sodium-1-naphthol-2-sulphonate (abbr. SNDS) have been studied in the present investigation. The ligands have the structures :

HBA

SNDS

Bjerrum-Calvin *pH*-titration technique^{7,8} has been employed to determine the stepwise protonation constants for the complexing agents HBA and SNDS as well as for the stepwise formation constants of the uranium (VI) complexes.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Stock Solutions : Metal Solution : Uranyl sulphate (BDH AnalaR) was dissolved in double distilled water. The solution was standardised⁹ and a 0.02M solution was obtained from the stock solution by dilution. *Ligand Solutions* : 0.02M solutions of HBA and SNDS (both BDH indicators) were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantities. *Sodium hydroxide* : Sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) was dissolved in a Pyrex beaker in distilled water free from CO₂ and was kept overnight over lime. The solution was standardised by titrating a diluted portion of it potentiometrically against a standard oxalic acid solution. Standard solutions were obtained by dilution with CO₂-free water.

Sodium perchlorate : A BDH AnalaR sample was dissolved in distilled water and was estimated¹⁰. Required solution 2.0M was prepared by dilution.

Perchloric acid : A sample (BDH AnalaR) was diluted and was standardised by titrating potentiometrically against a standard alkali. The standard solution (0.1M) was obtained by dilution.

Titration : Procedure adopted for titration has been described earlier¹. For observing the change in hydrogen ion concentration during titration a *pH*-indicator (Leeds and Northrup), with a glass-calomel electrode assembly, was used. The experiments were carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen and at a room temperature of 25°.

The titrations represented by Curve A (acid), Curve B (acid+ligand) and Curve C (acid +ligand +metal) (figs, 1, 2) were performed with three mixtures in which

Fig. 1. Titration curves of uranyl-HBA complex

A. HClO₄ (0.001M)

B. HBA (0.005M)

C. UO₂SO₄ (0.001M)

Titrant 0.100M NaOH.

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(i) the overall concentrations of HClO_4 in all the three mixtures (A, B, and C) were $0.001M$ and $0.0047M$ for UO_2^{2+} -HBA and UO_2^{2+} -SNDS systems respectively.

(ii) The overall concentrations of HBA and SNDS in the two mixtures (B and C) were $0.005M$ and $0.015M$ respectively.

(iii) the overall concentrations of UO_2^{2+} in the mixture (C) were $0.001M$ and $0.003M$ for UO_2^{2+} -HBA and UO_2^{2+} -SNDS systems respectively.

Fig. 2. Titration curves of uranyl-SNDS complex
 A. HClO_4 ($0.0047M$)
 B. SNDS ($0.0150M$)
 C. UO_2SO_4 ($0.0030M$)
 Titrant $0.9524M$ NaOH.

Fig. 3. Formation curve of proton-ligand system of HBA.

In all the mixtures a constant ionic medium of $0.1M(\text{NaClO}_4)$ was maintained and the volume in each case was 100 ml. The titrations were performed with $0.1M$ and *ca* $1.0M$ of NaOH for UO_2^{2+} -HBA and UO_2^{2+} -SNDS systems respectively. The titration curves (figs. 1 and 2) were drawn between pH and the volume of NaOH .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Formation Constants: Formation curves for the proton-ligand systems (figs. 3 and 4) and metal-ligand systems (figs. 5 and 6) were drawn between \bar{n}_A and pH

Fig. 4. Formation curve of proton-ligand system of SNDS.

and \bar{n} and pL respectively; where \bar{n}_A is the average number of protons attached per ligand molecule. \bar{n} is the average number of ligands associated with each metal ion and pL is the free ligand exponent. The values of these terms were obtained as described earlier¹.

Fig. 5. Formation curve of metal-ligand system of uranyl-HBA complex.

The computational methods described by Irving and Rossotti¹¹ were employed to determine the successive protonation constants for the ligands and successive formation constants for the uranyl complexes (Tables 1-4).

Colour Change : Colour changes were observed with the change of *pH* of the solution during titrations, which are tabulated (Tables 5 & 6).

TABLE 1

Protonation Constants of HBA

Method	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log \beta_2^H$ = $\log K_1^H K_2^H$
Interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values	12.05	8.95	21.00
Interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values	12.05	8.95	21.00
Mean	12.05	8.95	21.00

TABLE 2

Protonation Constants of SNDS

Method	$\log K_1^H$
Method of interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values	9.91
Average value method	9.87
Mean	9.89

Fig. 6. Formation curve of metal-ligand system of uranyl-SNDS complex.

TABLE 3

Formation Constants of UO_2^{2+} -HBA Complexes

Method	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$ = $\log K_1 K_2$
Interpolation at half \bar{n} values	14.00	9.00	23.00
Interpolation at various \bar{n} values	13.81	8.93	22.74
Mean	13.91	8.96	22.87

11. H. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.

TABLE 4

Formation Constants of UO_2^{2+} -SNDS Complexes

Method	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$ = $\log K_1 K_2$
Interpolation at half \bar{n} values	7.95	6.42	14.37
Midpoint slope	7.87	6.42	14.29
Correction term	7.93	6.43	14.36
Mean	7.92	6.42	14.34

TABLE

 UO_2^{2+} -SNDS System (fig. 1)

Solution	pH	Colour
Ligand (Curve B)	3.45—7.90	Colourless
	8.00—8.80	Pale yellow
	8.90 and above	Light yellow
Complex (Curve C)	3.35—3.95	Colourless
	4.15—6.75	Light to deep yellow
	6.95—7.75	Yellowish orange
	7.85—9.30	Orange
	9.30 and above	Bright yellow

TABLE 6

 UO_2^{2+} -HBA System (fig. 2)

Solution	pH	Colour
Ligand (Curve B)	2.65 and above	Yellow
Complex (Curve C)	2.60—3.05	Orange to reddish orange
	3.15—4.10	Red
	4.30—6.40	Blood red
	6.75—10.20	Turbidity appears and goes on increasing with gradual fading of colour
	10.70 and above	Yellow precipitate settles

A colour change is observed from colourless to light yellow at a pH range 8.00-8.90 in HBA (Table 5), which corresponds to the range of \bar{n}_4 values ≈ 2.0 -1.5. But, approximately equal amounts of LH^- and LH_2 are expected to be present in solution at $\bar{n}_4 \approx 1.5$ and hence it is inferred that LH_2 is colourless and LH^- is light yellow in colour.

In the case of UO_2^{2+} -HBA system (Table 5) a colour change from light to deep yellow is observed around pH 5.70 where the values of $\bar{n} \approx 1.0$. Thus, the species ML is believed to be yellow in colour. Another colour change from yellowish orange to orange is observed at pH 7.85 where \bar{n} corresponds to 1.5. At this value of \bar{n} the species ML and ML_2 appear to be present in equal proportions, the species ML_2 being orange.

Formation of a red colour at a pH range 3.15-4.10 is observed in the UO_2^{2+} -SNDS system (Table 6). In this case $\text{pH} \approx 3.80$ corresponds to $\bar{n} \approx 0.5$. At this value of \bar{n} the species M and ML are present in equal proportions. But in the present case M and L are yellow in colour. Therefore, it may be concluded that ML is red in colour. An increase in the intensity of the colour upto pH 6.40 again confirms the colour of the species ML to be red. This is due to the fact that $\text{pH} \approx 4.70$ corresponds $\bar{n} \approx 1.0$ where ML is the major species.

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